

FETCH-LIMITED SURFACE WAVE GROWTH INSIDE TROPICAL CYCLONES AND HURRICANE WIND SPEED RETRIEVAL

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1. INTRODUCTION

Despite the complicated temporal and spatial distributions of the hurricane wind field, many analyses have shown that the generated surface waves follow the same similarity relationship as those generated by steady winds in fetch-limited conditions. For example, Young [1] produces a sequence of numerically simulated directional wave spectra forced by model hurricane wind fields. Using the JONSWAP wave growth relationship of $\eta_{\#}(x_{\#})$ [2], he derives the effective fetch from the significant wave height H_s . The effective fetch is then used to compute the expected peak wave period T_p based on the JONSWAP fetch-limited growth function of $\omega_{\#}(x_{\#})$. The T_p from numerical model and fetch-limited computation are in very good agreement. The dimensionless parameters are given by $\eta_{\#} = \eta_{rms}^2 g^2 / U_{10}^4$, $\omega_{\#} = \omega_p U_{10} / g$, $x_{\#} = xg / U_{10}^2$, $\eta_{rms} = H_s / 4$, $\omega_p = 2\pi / T_p$, U_{10} is reference neutral wind speed at 10 m elevation, x is fetch, and g is gravitational acceleration

Subsequently, Young [3, 4] report the results from examining more than 20 years directional buoy recordings. Restricting the data segments to the condition that the buoy is within 8 times of the radius of maximum hurricane wind speed from the hurricane center, he shows that the key parameters that define the directional wave spectra in the hurricane waves are not distinguishable from those observed in ideal steady wind fields. As a consequence of the wave spectral similarity, the wave growth function given as $\eta_{\#}(\omega_{\#})$ is the same for both wave fields generated by hurricane

winds and steady winds. The similarity relation connects the three wind and wave variables (U_{10} , H_s , T_p), which will be referred to as the wind-wave triplets from here on.

The fetch- and duration-limited nature of wave growth inside hurricanes is further clarified with airborne scanning radar (SRA) wave measurements [5, 6] in hurricane hunting missions. Using the 60 wave spectra of Hurricane Bonnie 1998 reported by Wright et al. [7] and 12 wave spectra of Hurricane Ivan 2004 reported by Black et al. [8], Hwang [9] presents an analysis of the wave growth inside hurricanes not only as the similarity function $\eta_{\#}(\omega_{\#})$ but also the fetch and duration functions: $\eta_{\#}(x_{\#})$, $\omega_{\#}(x_{\#})$, $\eta_{\#}(t_{\#})$, and $\omega_{\#}(t_{\#})$. The dimensionless duration is given by $t_{\#} = tg / U_{10}$. The data provide sufficient information to divide the hurricane coverage area into 3 sectors (right, left and back).

The 60 wave spectra reported by Wright et al. [7] represent about a quarter of the full suite of spectra collected in that hurricane hunter mission. The full set in fact contains 233 spectra along 10 radial groundtracks. With the broader coverage in the full data set, it is feasible to derive a much better resolution in the azimuthal and radial variation of the surface wave development inside hurricanes (section 2). Using the fetch-limited wave growth property, an algorithm to obtain hurricane wind speed using the dominant wave properties is described (sec. 3). A summary is given in Sec. 4.

2. SURFACE WAVE DEVELOPMENT INSIDE HURRICANES

The SRA wave measurements inside Hurricane Bonnie 1998 reported here span the time between 2030 UTC 24 August to 0144 UTC 25 August. Detailed discussions of the mission have been presented in [7] and [10]. Figs. 1a to 1c show the wind-wave triplets (U_{10} , H_s , T_p) plotted with respect to the position relative to the moving hurricane center. The flight track and the hurricane eye positions on the earth coordinates are given in Fig. 1 of [7], which is reproduced in Fig. 1f for reference. During the 4.7 h data acquisition time, the hurricane was moving in a steady NNW direction. The hurricane advancing velocity is estimated from the hurricane center positions to be about (4.5 m/s, 13°N), here the azimuth angle increases counterclockwise (CCW). Using the hurricane heading as the reference, the dimensionless wave variance and peak frequency are plotted in Figs. 1d and 1e. When referenced to the hurricane heading subscript h is added to the plotting coordinates (x , y).

As the analysis given in [9] shows, the growth of surface waves inside a hurricane (except for the region near the hurricane eye) follows the established fetch- and duration-limited relationships. As a result, given the effective fetch or duration, it is feasible to compute the wind-wave triplets (U_{10} , H_s , T_p) knowing only one of the three variables. Using the full set of the Bonnie 1998 SRA wind and wave data, the azimuthal and radial dependence of the wind fetch inside a hurricane are established. The effective fetch $x_{\eta x}$ and x_{ox} for wave height and wave period respectively can be expressed as a linear function of the radial distance from the hurricane center r (the distances in the following equation is given in km and the azimuth angle ϕ is referenced to the hurricane heading, positive CCW)

$$\begin{aligned} x_{\eta x}(r, \phi) &= a_{\eta x}(\phi) \cdot r + A_{\eta x}(\phi) \\ x_{ox}(r, \phi) &= a_{ox}(\phi) \cdot r + A_{ox}(\phi) \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

The azimuthal variations of the slopes ($a_{\eta x}$ and a_{ox}) and the intercepts ($A_{\eta x}$ and A_{ox}) are presented as lookup tables (Table 1).

The fetch-limited growth functions can be used to estimate the key wave parameters of significant wave height and dominant wave period given the knowledge of wind speed and wind fetch [9]:

Fig. 1. (a) U_{10} , (b) H_s , (c) T_p , (d) $\log(\eta\#)$, and (e) $\omega\#$ measured by the SRA inside Hurricane Bonnie 1998; (f) reproduces Fig. 1 of [7] and shows the longitude and latitude coordinates of the flight tracks with the positions of the hurricane centers superimposed.

$$\begin{aligned} H_{sw} &= 8.10 \times 10^{-4} U_{10}^{1.19} x_{\eta x}^{0.405} \\ T_{pw} &= 9.28 \times 10^{-2} U_{10}^{0.526} x_{ox}^{0.237} \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

The subscript w for H_s and T_p in (2) emphasizes that the wave properties obtained from the fetch relationship represent the wind sea components. Figure 2 shows a comparison of the SRA in-situ measurements of H_s and T_p with those computed from (2). The results are given in terms of the ratios $R_{HU} = H_{sw} / H_s(SRA)$ and $R_{TU} = T_{pw} / T_p(SRA)$. They are plotted as a function of the radial distance from the hurricane center on the left column, and as a function of the azimuthal angle with respect to the hurricane heading on the right column.

Table 1. Lookup tables for the coefficients of the effective fetches (1).

ϕ (°)	$A_{\eta x}$ (km)	$a_{\eta x}$	A_{ox} (km)	a_{ox}
-13	100.00	0.50	100.00	0.50
7	94.72	0.14	-104.50	3.60
22	108.79	-0.01	79.43	1.12
67	77.47	0.93	181.65	0.71
115	-33.58	1.78	-9.26	2.60
157	37.75	0.40	27.46	0.29
200	43.45	0.70	40.29	0.37
242	134.73	0.69	114.20	0.37
270	107.65	0.46	160.67	-0.07
292	149.25	0.30	135.62	0.45
330	109.42	0.81	35.62	1.59
347	100.00	0.50	100.00	0.50
367	94.72	0.14	-104.50	3.60

Excluding the region close to the hurricane center (during the period of data acquisition, the radius of maximum wind speed R_m is about 75 km), the ratios

Fig. 2. (Top row): The ratio between the wind-sea wave height H_{sw} computed with U_{10} and the $\eta_{\#}(x_{\#})$ growth function and the SRA-measured H_s , plotted against (a) radial distance from the hurricane center, and (b) azimuth angle with respect to the hurricane heading. (Bottom row): Same as the (Top row) but for T_{pw} computed with U_{10} and the $\omega_{\#}(x_{\#})$ growth function.

generally stay within 1.0 ± 0.10 . Specifically, for $r > 75$ km, the average and standard deviation of R_{HU} and R_{TU} are 1.00 ± 0.089 and 0.99 ± 0.069 . The corresponding statistics of SRA measured H_s and T_p are 7.77 ± 1.85 m, 10.86 ± 1.27 s; the fetch-law computed H_{sw} and T_{pw} are 7.73 ± 1.77 m, 10.77 ± 1.33 s.

Using the procedure described above, the dominant wave information can be calculated from the hurricane wind field. Figure 3 shows the result obtained for the archived HRD wind field at 1830 UTC 24 Aug 1998, which is the closest time to the SRA measurements (2030 UTC 24 August to 0144 UTC 25 August) with the gridded data available at the archive site (http://www.hwind.co/legacy_data/). The maximum 1-min sustained surface wind speed is about 44 m/s (category 2) at 78 km NE of center (Fig. 3a). The computed H_{sw} , T_{pw} , $\eta_{\#}$, and $\omega_{\#}$ are illustrated in Figs. 3b-e. The azimuthal and radial variations of the wind-wave triplets and the corresponding dimensionless $\eta_{\#}$ and $\omega_{\#}$ show rather complex patterns. In general terms, the wave height is larger on the right hand side; the wave period is longer in the front half; the young seas are at the rear right quarter and the older seas occupy the left half plane.

3. HURRICANE WIND RETRIEVAL

Using the fetch-limited growth functions, the wind speed can be obtained from H_s or T_p accompanied with the fetch input [9]:

$$\begin{aligned} U_{10} &= 397.46 H_s^{0.841} x_{\eta x}^{-0.341} \\ U_{10} &= 91.49 T_p^{1.900} x_{\omega x}^{-0.450} \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

Fig. 3. An example illustrating the application of the wind-wave growth functions to derive wave properties from the hurricane wind field: (a) HRD U_{10} field for Hurricane Bonnie at 1830 UTC 24 Aug 1998, and the computed wave fields of (b) H_{sw} , (c) T_{pw} , (d) $\eta_{\#}$, and (e) $\omega_{\#}$.

Figure 4 shows the ratios R_{UH} and R_{UT} of retrieved U_{10} using H_s and T_p vs. the HRD U_{10} . In the same format of Fig. 2, the results are plotted as a function of the radial distance from the hurricane center on the left column, and as a function of the azimuth angle with respect to the hurricane heading on the right column. For $r > 75$ km, the average and standard deviation of R_{UH} and R_{UT} are 1.00 ± 0.083 and 1.03 ± 0.16 . The corresponding statistics of HRD U_{10} vs. H_s and T_p derived U_{10} are 37.38 ± 6.15 , 37.46 ± 6.72 , and 37.70 ± 6.15 m/s.

Fig. 4. Same as Fig. 2 but for wind speed inversion using H_s and T_p .

4. SUMMARY

The robust wind wave growth functions established with ideal fetch-limited and quasi-steady wind conditions (e.g., [11-13]; and references therein) have been observed to be applicable to wind generated waves under considerably more varying conditions, including hurricanes [1, 3, 4, 14, 15] and rapidly

accelerating and decelerating wind fields such as those encountered in mountain gap winds [16-19].

With the deployment of SRA in hurricane hunter missions, the detailed 2D wavenumber spectra have advanced significantly our understanding of the wave conditions inside hurricanes. In this paper, the fetch-limited nature of wave development inside hurricanes is analyzed to provide good resolutions in azimuth and radial range for the effective fetches of H_s and T_p . The azimuthal and range dependency of the effective wind fetches for wave height and wave period are given in lookup tables (Table 1). With the help of the effective fetch, the complete wind wave triplets (U_{10} , H_s , T_p) inside a hurricane can be obtained knowing only one of the three. Applying the wind wave growth function, an algorithm for hurricane wind speed retrieval from H_s or T_p is presented. Alternatively, given the hurricane wind field, the H_s and T_p fields can be computed to investigate the critical parameters such as energy exchange rate and exchange velocity across the air-sea interface (e.g., [9, 20-21]).

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5. REFERENCES

- [1] Young, I. R. 1988: Parametric hurricane wave prediction model. *ASCE J. Waterway, Port, Coastal and Ocean Eng.*, **114**, 637-652.
- [2] Hasselmann, K. et al., 1973: Measurements of wind-wave growth and swell decay during the Joint North Sea Wave Project (JONSWAP). *Deutsch. Hydrogr. Z.*, Suppl. **A8(12)**, 95pp.
- [3] Young, I. R., 1998: Observations of the spectra of hurricane generated waves. *Ocean Eng.*, **25**, 261-276.
- [4] Young, I. R., 2006: Directional spectra of hurricane wind waves. *J. Geophys. Res.*, **111**, C08020.
- [5] Walsh, E. J., D. W. Hancock, D. E. Hines, R. N. Swift, and J. F. Scott, 1985: Directional wave spectra measured with the surface contour radar. *J. Phys. Oceanogr.*, **15**, 566-592.
- [6] Walsh, E. J., D. W. Hancock, D. E. Hines, R. N. Swift, and J. F. Scott, 1989: An observation of the directional wave spectrum evolution from shoreline to fully developed. *J. Phys. Oceanogr.*, **19**, 670-690.
- [7] Wright, C. W., E. J. Walsh, D. Vandemark, W. B. Krabill, A. W. Garcia, S. H. Houston, M. D. Powell, P. G. Black, and F. D. Marks, 2001: Hurricane directional wave spectrum spatial variation in the open ocean. *J. Phys. Oceanogr.*, **31**, 2472-2488.
- [8] Black, P. G., E. A. D'Asaro, W. M. Drennan, J. R. French, P. P. Niiler, T. B. Sanford, E. J. Terrill, E. J. Walsh, and J. A. Zhang, 2007: Air-sea exchange in hurricanes: Synthesis of observations from the coupled boundary layer air-sea transfer experiment. *Bulle. Am. Meteorol. Soc.*, **88**, 357-374.
- [9] Hwang, P. A., 2016: Fetch- and duration-limited nature of surface wave growth inside tropical cyclones: With applications to air-sea exchange and remote sensing. *J. Phys. Oceanogr.*, **46**, 41-56, doi: 10.1175/JPO-D-15-0173.1.
- [10] Moon, I.-J., I. Ginis, T. Hara, H. L. Tolman, C. W. Wright, and E. J. Walsh, 2003: Numerical simulation of sea surface directional wave spectra under hurricane wind forcing. *J. Phys. Oceanogr.*, **33**, 1680-1706.
- [11] Hwang, P. A., and D. W. Wang, 2004: Field measurements of duration limited growth of wind-generated ocean surface waves at young stage of development. *J. Phys. Oceanogr.*, **34**, 2316-2326. (Corrigendum, **35**, 268-270, 2005).
- [12] Hwang, P. A., 2006: Duration- and fetch-limited growth functions of wind-generated waves parameterized with three different scaling wind velocities. *J. Geophys. Res.*, **111**, C02005, doi:10.1029/2005JC003180.
- [13] Zakharov, V. E., S. I. Badulin, P. A. Hwang, and G. Caulliez, 2015: Universality of sea wave growth and its physical roots. *J. Fluid Mech.*, **780**, 503-535, doi:10.1017/jfm.2015.468.
- [14] Young, I. R., 2003: A review of the sea state generated by hurricanes. *Ocean Eng.*, **25**, 261-276.
- [15] Young, I. R., and J. Vinoth, 2013: An "extended fetch" model for the spatial distribution of tropical cyclone wind-waves as observed by altimeter. *Ocean Eng.*, **70**, 14-24.
- [16] García-Nava, H., F. J. Ocampo-Torres, P. Osuna, and M. A. Donelan, 2009: Wind stress in the presence of swell under moderate to strong wind conditions. *J. Geophys. Res.*, **114**, C12008, doi:10.1029/2009JC005389.
- [17] Ocampo-Torres, F. J., H. García-Nava, R. Durazo, P. Osuna, G. M. Díaz Méndez, and H. C. Graber, 2011: The INTOA Experiment: A study of ocean-atmosphere interactions under moderate to strong offshore winds and opposing swell conditions, in the Gulf of Tehuantepec, Mexico. *Bound.-Layer Meteorol.*, doi: 10.1007/s10546-010-9561-5, **138**, 433-451.
- [18] Romero, L., and W. K. Melville, 2010: Airborne observations of fetch-limited waves in the Gulf of Tehuantepec. *J. Phys. Oceanogr.*, **40**, 441-465.
- [19] Hwang, P. A., H. García-Nava, and F. J. Ocampo-Torres, 2011: Observations of wind wave development in mixed seas and unsteady wind forcing. *J. Phys. Oceanogr.*, **41**, 2343-2362, doi: 10.1175/JPO-D-11-044.1.
- [20] Hwang, P. A., and M. A. Sletten, 2008: Energy dissipation of wind-generated waves and whitecap coverage. *J. Geophys. Res.*, **113**, C02012, doi:10.1029/2007JC004277 (Corrigendum, **114**, C02015, doi:10.1029/2008JC005244, 2009).
- [21] Hwang, P. A., 2009: Estimating the effective energy transfer velocity at air-sea interface. *J. Geophys. Res.*, **114**, C11011, doi:10.1029/2009JC005497.